

D 6.1

Dissemination, Collaboration & Communication

Master

[First version]

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Technical References

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Executive Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The target of ULTIMATE project is to act as a catalyst for “Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis” (WSIS) in which water/wastewater plays a key role both as a reusable resource and as a vector for energy and materials to be extracted, treated, stored and reused within a dynamic socio-economic and business oriented industrial ecosystem.

Effective communication and dissemination of the progress and results of ULTIMATE is of major importance to maximise the impact of the project and achieve long-lasting results.

D6.1 ‘Dissemination, Communication & Collaboration Master Plan’ is a framework for communication, dissemination and collaboration planned within ULTIMATE that empowers all partners to engage with multiple audiences during the lifecycle of the project. It describes the overall communication strategy of the consortium, and functions as a guide for project partners when publishing about or on behalf of the project.

This baseline document for communication and dissemination activities will be updated twice during the project lifetime – in M25 and M40, as the project partners get new insights about the major target groups and stakeholders, identify early adopters and further synergy partners.

Almost all project partners have been allocated resources in the WP6 to communicate, connect, create synergies, and support learning and policy making in order to maximise the visibility of the project. WP6 will be coordinated by the European Science Communication Institute (ESCI), with substantial strategic input from KWR and WE, plus support from all partners.

Spelling Guidelines

Standardised British Spelling should be used in all documents. Generic terms are spelled in lower case, specific terms and proper names are spelled with initial capitals.

Disclaimer

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1. Communication and Dissemination Management

1.1. Roles and Responsibilities of partners

According to Article 29 of the Grant Agreement, all partners are required to communicate and disseminate their results. Furthermore, all partners are requested to “promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner”, according to Article 38 of the Grant Agreement.

All partners are therefore expected to be proactively looking for communication and dissemination opportunities as well as to contribute to communication and dissemination efforts of the Consortium, to reach the European-wide audience.

The European Science Communication Institute (ESCI) is leading the work package 6 (WP6) and the coordination of communication, dissemination, and collaboration activities. All partners are requested to contribute to the activities of WP6.

1.1.1. Open access to scientific publications

According to the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary must guarantee open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. For more details, please refer to the clause 29.2 “Open access to scientific publications” of the Grant and Consortium Agreement.

1.1.2. EC acknowledgment

Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

“ This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869318” .

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

1.1.3. Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

This publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

1.2. Procedure of approval within the consortium

1.2.1. Scientific or Technical Publications

According to Article 29 of the Grant Agreement, all partners are required to ask for permission when publishing scientific publications (in any medium).

During the project and for a period of one year after the end of the project, prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the project coordinator and to the party or parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication will be permitted.

1.2.2. Communication Material

During the project, ESCI and other partners will produce a variety of different communication materials, such as brochures, videos, articles, interviews, social media posts, etc. These communication tools require a different approval procedure compared to scientific articles, as they do not contain detailed IPR relevant issues.

Before the printing of brochures and the publication of videos, the project coordinator will be reviewing and approving the materials. For videos on the demo sites, also the respective demo site leader will be required to approve the video before publication.

For official ULTIMATE press releases, the approval will be required from the coordinator. Press releases from the partners will be under the responsibility of the partners and do not require official approval from the coordinator.

For journalistic articles and interviews only the organisations or persons mentioned in the publications will be required to approve or to proofread the content. No official approval from the Consortium is foreseen. These publications have a journalistic approach and interference by interested parties would be counterproductive for the distribution success. Final articles and interviews produced will be shared with the

dissemination partner and be included in the monitoring table for the ULTIMATE project.

No approval is needed for social media posts done by ESCI on the Twitter or LinkedIn channels. For partners creating posts, tweets, and retweets in social media in frame of the project, the authors should make a reference to ULTIMATE by linking it to #ultimatewaterEU or connecting to the project by writing @ULTIMATEWaterEU.

2. Dissemination, Communication and Collaboration Plan

2.1. Goal and strategy

ULTIMATE aims to become a catalyst of a particular type of industrial symbiosis – henceforth termed “Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis” (WSIS) – in which water/wastewater plays a key role both as a reusable resource. It will also act as a vector for energy and materials to be extracted, treated, stored and reused within a dynamic socio-economic and business oriented industrial ecosystem. The applied technologies will benefit from the result of the project. Since they vary greatly, the communication and dissemination activities will have to target diverse audiences.

Communication, collaboration and engagement are pillars of excellence and innovation on a par with our technical endeavours. Project communication is vital to supporting the ULTIMATE goals and will specifically seek to facilitate significant broader ambitions:

- (1) Promote active engagement and knowledge sharing between 9 demonstration sites, project partners, end-users, a range of professional stakeholders and engage with citizens;
- (2) Boost external communication and promotion of the Technology Evidence Base (D1.6 & D1.7), case studies, Marketplace for Water, Energy, Materials in a WSIS (D5.5), experiences and outcomes, so as to widely promote the principles of ULTIMATE; and
- (3) Establish a knowledge legacy, through an ongoing platform to promote and share project principles, support creation of new spin offs, exploit new business opportunities and long-term jobs in water supply.

The main goals of the communication and dissemination defined for ULTIMATE are:

- **Raise awareness** of the market of water-intensive industries about the project results.
- **Increase the attractiveness** of water-smart industrial symbiosis among citizens, business communities and decision-makers.
- **Foster implementation and replication of ULTIMATE concepts** by industrial facilities and other stakeholders.
- **Engage in a dialogue** with industrial facilities and stakeholders about the project solutions to **foster exploitation** of the ULTIMATE results.
- **Build a community** of actors committed to **replicate** the ULTIMATE solutions in other European cities and countries.

- **Provide new insights** to the water-intensive industry in the areas of water-smart industrial symbiosis and circular economy.

Communication, dissemination and collaboration strategy and specific actions will unfold and intensify as the project advances. The project starts with no project results available, the communication will focus on raising general awareness and interest for the project among wider audiences. In a next step with the first results at hand, communication and dissemination activities will focus on timely release of results and updates, tailored for different target audiences. From this phase onwards, communication and dissemination activities will be diversified into targeted actions towards specific stakeholder groups. With demonstration sites in place and more results available, communication and dissemination activities will focus on the promotion of the adoption of ULTIMATE approaches and technologies. Moreover, communication and dissemination activities will include citizen engagement to foster acceptance and exploitation of the project results.

2.2. Target audiences

As a large-scale demonstration project, a primary focus of the ULTIMATE consortium is to achieve a maximum transfer of information and shareable research results to the professional audiences that can best make use of it. Given that the circular economy is driven by fundamental shifts to mindset and collaboration, this may be a dynamic, changing and widespread group of actors, rather than a siloed, simple target audience.

As mentioned above, the project will be dealing with a variety of target groups. Target audiences for the projects' knowledge feature a pan-European spread are identified and segmented in the following main communication and dissemination target audience groups:

- **Business & Investors**
- **Policy makers & Politicians**
- **Civil society & Consumers**

Business & Investors	Policy makers & Politicians	Civil Society & Consumers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy suppliers & operators, • Water service providers, • New digital services, • Agro-food business, • Food processing, • Beverages companies, • Chemical industries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local authorities, • Policy makers at international level, • Regional & national decision makers, • Environmental agencies, • European decision makers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value chain suppliers, • emerging players in new digital services and business models, • Neighbouring industries and sectors, • General public.

Figure 1 Main Target Audiences and Stakeholder Groups

In accordance with the project call, as primary target audience business/industry & investors have been identified. Accelerating the project results to industrial clusters, smart industry strategies and policies make policy makers & politicians the second important target audience in the hierarchy. As third target audience civil society & consumers moving forward to leading key players through our local events and communication.

Transversal segments

In addition, ULTIMATE is not only working to develop awareness and action in one value chain in transition to a circular economy, but three! While water stakeholders identified above are the critical entry point and target audiences, the project is operating at a nexus of water, materials, and energy.

Not all of these processes are directly targeted, but transversal segments to target with ULTIMATE knowledge and outputs include food and fodder, nutrient and material markets, biogas, electricity and heat providers and the consumer food industry.

ULTIMATE builds upon work of two Water in the Circular Economy H2020 project, NextGen and Hydrousa. With regards to NextGen in particular, ensuring sustainability and critical mass of knowledge developed and audience/market for its knowledge products. ULTIMATE will provide additional content and functionality, of relevance to industrial symbiosis, to NextGen’s online CE infrastructure, consisting of the NextGen CE Marketplace, Technology Evidence Base (TEB) and support tools for the symbiotic opportunities, whose long-term viability is guaranteed as they are adopted by Water Europe as part of its Water Innovation Europe programme.

In ULTIMATE, data from the demonstration cases are collected, integrated, and harmonised in the Technology Evidence Base (TEB) developed in NextGen. Synergies between both projects are built by integrating the different concepts of symbioses and the ULTIMATE technologies into the existing NextGen TEB.

Figure 2 ULTIMATE nexus audience segments and solutions in combination with the NextGen project

Specific dissemination and communication actions to reach these audiences may multiply entry points in the number of trade press publications, trade shows, professional associations and even LinkedIn groups, for example, to interact with. While this adds additional effort, it also adds opportunity, especially for a substantiated, Technology Evidence Base of solutions and deliverables. Promoting these resources will help establish a knowledge legacy as an ongoing platform to promote and share

the principals of the project to connect the circular economy and the nexus between water, energy, and materials.

Business segment

ULTIMATE has a high exploitation for scalable results and new business opportunities within a circular economy in all three of the projects key areas – materials, energy, water – and beyond.

In conjunction with exploitation partner Strane Innovation, dissemination and communication will support actions towards business, exploitation and investment opportunities in water industry and industrial sectors with interest in reusing water. Several specific segments, such as agricultural and chemical will be fertile target audiences for the project technology evidence base, business case studies and even spin off incubation.

For these business segments, tangible proof points and results as a cornerstone communication piece is key. Again, deliverables in the Technology Evidence Base and marketplace.

WP6 lead and key partners in exploitation and demonstration sites and will have to assess relative strength and promise of deliverables, monitoring results and business potential to prioritise which of these areas is deserving of the most focus. Collaborating with EU policy and policy professional segments follows below as part of the activities lead by Water Europe. Discussions with Water Europe for business marketplace events in target segments may also support this.

Civil Society and the Public

ULTIMATE targets several direct citizen involvements as a circular economy requires a common change of mentality and behaviour to create an economic system that uses resources more intelligently and respectfully.

Achieving this shared mindset shift is key and why it is essential to get all involved parties around the table, listen to each other and act jointly. The project practices an approach called “Communities of Practice” (CoP) as a method to establish a circular water economy in the long term with economic advantages, social and ecological side effects that benefit us all. These communities of practice are being deployed at a number of demonstration sites. Communication actions, such as infographics, print materials, case studies and visual supports will help increase their effectiveness.

ULTIMATE acknowledges the major importance of science communication to act as an impact multiplier and through NTNU, which defines, measures, and supports quality in science communication, improving effectiveness in dialogue between science and wider publics. For example, additional activities that are also built around the Case Studies but are not demonstration activities including stakeholder engagement and consultation for problem identification as well as collaboration with stakeholders to develop or customise novel ideas and solutions, prior to demonstration. The arts and humanities are critical tools for engagement supported by Multi use play spaces and immersive narratives articulated within eXtended Realities (XR) spaces associated with the case studies. We will support inclusive stakeholder co-design for innovations through gamified visualization of system modelling results and scenarios (WP2) and further work in developing and promoting the concept, method and practice behind WSIS-oriented Living Labs (LLs), working with existing Labs in the case regions to support their further evolution.

2.3. Key messages

Ensuring engagement with different target groups, the key messages have to be tailored to meet the requirements of the respective groups, addressing their possible benefits.

This first draft of the Communication, Dissemination and Collaboration Master Plan cannot define all the relevant messages yet. We will thus anticipate multiple messages as the project evolves. In the update version of the Master Plan in M25 and M40 those key messages will be included respectively.

ULTIMATE is taking place at a critical convergence of social, ecological, and economic factors that will facilitate dissemination and communication impact and stresses the actions and messages. The ULTIMATE action plans during the project to leverage three key dynamics:

Table 1 ULTIMATE Key Dynamics

Business & investors	Reducing costs or generating new revenues in the CE speaks volumes to industry in today’ s economy. Medium-to-long term ability to leverage investment and share price affected by ability to address sustainability issues. Manage emerging legislative risks and requirements.
Policy makers & Politicians	Eager to stimulate jobs and growth while meeting legally binding and ambitious environmental targets, welcome new value chains and efficiency. Regional clusters and interconnections especially

	effective – see connection to Water Team France (Advisory Board).
Civil Society & Consumers	Companies meet their expectations in sustainability or face commercial consequences – from switching suppliers to reward sustainability to reputation damage and regulatory reporting – see T4.1 on norms and link to Global News Publishers (Advisory Board).

3. Visual identity

To make sure that different messages sent by various project partners to multiple target groups will have a consistent and professional look, ESCI developed an impactful visual identity of the project, based on its thematic focus. The predominant colours are blue, green, yellow, and black, where blue represents water reuse, green material reuse and yellow energy exploitation from wastewater.

The colour palette goes from green to different shades of blue, one shade of grey and black, to convey several levels of information, if needed.

Colours

C 85% M 30% Y 20% K 0% #0089b2	C 50% M 10% Y 80% K 0% #94b654	C 0% M 25% Y 100% K 0% #fdc300	C 40% M 0% Y 0% K 10% #96cae5	C 45% M 0% Y 0% K 40% #6795ab	C 0% M 0% Y 0% K 40% #b2b2b1	C 0% M 0% Y 0% K 90% #3c3c3b
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Figure 3 ULTIMATE Colour Scale

3.1. Logo

The logo reflects the core of the project and will be used for internal and external project communication (document templates, presentations, project website and other communication materials).

In parallel to the visual identity, light blue represents water reuse, green material reuse and yellow energy exploitation from wastewater within the project.

The tagline of the logo “Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis” underlines the project context appropriately.

Figure 4 ULTIMATE Logo with Tagline

The Logo is available in different formats. The single drop was chosen as recognition factor. For the different topics to be investigated in the project, the drop is also available in the single colours blue, yellow, and green. To further enable the use for different types of contexts, the logo is also available with and without the tagline.

Figure 5 All ULTIMATE Logo Versions

The design of the ULTIMATE logo not only reflects the project idea, but also meets the standard assessment criteria for a good logo.

Table 2 Assessment Criteria of the Project's Logo

Logo features	Criteria met
Readability and ability to stand out in different contexts;	√
Good performance both in small and big dimension ;	√
Potential to evolve into other graphic materials (e.g. a graphic layout for brochure, postcards, newsletters, website that are clearly inspired by the logo.);	√
Ability to deliver the project's topic ;	√
Uniqueness and ability to differentiate from other existing logos;	√
Applicable in a multi-country context ;	√
Ability to capture attention in cluttered/confused context .	√

3.2. Fonts

The font has been selected in accordance with the project focus, reflecting its technical character. Project partners can download the font free of charge. Alternatively, standard fonts Roboto, Arial or Franklin Gothic can be used since they correspond to the selected optics and are installed by default in all the regular office programmes.

Logo: Big John (partly modified)

Find here: <https://www.dafontfree.io/big-john-slim-joe-font-free/>

Slogan: Roboto Black

Find here: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Roboto>

3.3. Templates

Furthermore, templates for the official project documentation (deliverables, presentations, participants list, etc.) have been developed in coherence with the visual identity of ULTIMATE.

The figure displays 12 Word document templates arranged in a 3x4 grid. Each template includes the ULTIMATE logo and a footer with project information.

- Meeting Minutes (Page 1):** Features a large ULTIMATE logo watermark, a title field, and a date field (17/07/2020).
- Meeting Minutes (Page 2):** Contains 'Meeting Information' and 'Attendance List' tables.
- Meeting Minutes (Page 3):** Contains a 'List of absentees' table.
- Interim Report (Page 1):** Features a large ULTIMATE logo watermark, a title field, and a date field (17/07/2020).
- Interim Report (Page 2):** Contains a 'Table of Contents' table.
- Interim Report (Page 3):** Contains a 'Document History' table and a '1. Publishable summary' section.
- Title of the document (Page 1):** Features a large ULTIMATE logo watermark, a title field, and a date field (17/07/2020).
- Title of the document (Page 2):** Contains a 'Technical References' table.
- Title of the document (Page 3):** Contains a 'Summary' section and a 'Disclaimer' section.

Figure 6 ULTIMATE Word Templates

Figure 7 ULTIMATE Power Point Template (Starting slides)

4. Communication Channels

The advances and results of the project will be communicated and disseminated through multiple channels to reach various target audiences. Online communication channels, such as the ULTIMATE website and social media channels will play a prominent role.

Communication will include activities aimed at increasing the awareness about the project among a large audience, including the general public, decision-makers, press, etc. Dissemination activities will focus on knowledge and information transfer for specific communities: industry stakeholders, researchers, policymakers, etc. to foster the exploitability of the project results.

As part of the dissemination activities, each partner will use their own database of stakeholders to disseminate ULTIMATE-related content.

4.1. Project Website

The project website – www.ultimatewater.eu – is a reference point for the project communication and dissemination activities. Was launched 31 August 2020 (M3). As of M1, a landing page was already available. The project website will be constantly maintained and updated.

During the first phase of the project (M4-24), the website will present the main objectives of the project, description of the demonstration sites and the main technologies. It will establish links to social media channels and publish relevant updates.

During the second project phase (M25-M48), with the results available, the website will contain regular updates and will act as the platform to distribute non-confidential contents (scientific publications, articles, press releases, project updates, etc.).

The following website structure is envisioned:

Table 3 ULTIMATE Website Structure

Landing page	The Project	WSIS	Demo Cases	News & Events	Results	Contact
News & Events	About – Key Activities - Impact	Key technologies	1 Taragona (ES)	Event Calendar	Academic publications	Coordinator Contact
Interactive Map with 9 demo cases	Partners	ULTIMATE solutions	2 Nieuw Prinseland (NL)	Articles / Publications	Public deliverables	Communication Contact
Key technologies teaser	Project Organisation		3 Rosignano Solvay, Cecina (IT)	Press releases	Best practice guideline	
Online tools	External Advisory Board		4 Nafplio (EL)		Info material / Brochure / digital flyer card	
Stakeholder & citizen engagement	Related topics		5 Lleida (ES), Ostrava (CZ)			
			6 Karmiel, Shafdan (IL)			
			7 Tain, Scotland (UK)			
			8 Saint Maurice, L'Exil (FR)			
		9 Kalundborg (DK)				

The website will have engaging design and user-friendly navigation. The different sections will have the following content:

Table 4 ULTIMATE Website Features

Features	Description
Landing Page	The main project overview, demo cases and links to the digital tools and stakeholder engagement platform will be included for easy access.
The Project	A brief presentation of the project, the expected results and its objectives, key technologies as well as information about the project

	partners will be provided. Also, the project partners will be introduced and their role within the project presented. Mutual links to partner websites will be included, as well as their logo.
WSIS	Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis will be introduced as a special case of industrial symbiosis in the context of circular economy. Links to respective platforms will be included.
Demo cases	Presentation of the demo sites for large-scale replication of the ULTIMATE concept will be presented with a short profile and their respective water-recycling and water reuse techniques explained.
News & Events	Project-related news, relevant events, as well as press releases and publications will be published.
Results	All the academic publications, public deliverables and best practice guidelines from WP2 will be published as well as the key presentations and information materials e.g. digital brochure or flyer postcard.
Contact	A contact form, as well contact details of the project coordinator and communication WP Leader (ESCI) will be provided.
Follow us	Links to the ULTIMATE profiles on social media platforms such as Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube will be provided to ensure the highest visibility of the project on the web and to increase the project's outreach.
Internal Section	Link to the project document archive included.
Privacy Policy	Legal information about the website, as well as data protection regulations will be provided in this section.

4.2. Social Media Channels

Social media will play an important role for the project outreach. An “ULTIMATE community” will be created to increase the visibility and impact of the results published mainly on Twitter and LinkedIn. Project videos will be shared through YouTube.

The amount and nature of posts and tweets will vary during the project. At the initial stage of the project, relevant external scientific and journalistic articles, as well as

information about the project partners will be published, increasing the outreach and keep multiple audiences interested.

Starting from M12, when the first project results are expected the social media will be used for promoting the results and benefits of the project, fostering further exploitation.

Table 5 ULTIMATE Social Media Channels Overview

Channel	Description
Twitter	<p>Project Twitter account @ULTIMATEWaterEU was created and customised according to the visual identity of the project.</p> <p>The Twitter account will be used to engage with relevant associations, potential partners, the press and as part of the WSIS and renewable energy discussions.</p> <p>The hashtag used for the project is #ULTIMATEWaterEU, accompanied by #H2020, #WSIS #circulareconomy, #waterrecycling, #businessmodelinnovation #watersmartsociety.</p>
LinkedIn	<p>A project LinkedIn page was created and customised according to the visual identity of the project.</p> <p>Project results and news will be posted both on the ULTIMATE LinkedIn page, as well as in relevant groups. Thanks to the use of relevant hashtags, further users that do not follow the project on the LinkedIn page will be reached. All partners are encouraged to redistribute ULTIMATE content through their personal and corporate LinkedIn account accounts.</p> <p>The hashtags used for the project are #ULTIMATEWaterEU, #H2020, #WSIS, and #circulareconomy.</p>
Youtube	<p>Video content featuring the demo sites, as well as interviews with project partners and external experts will be developed and shared on the YouTube channel to attract stakeholders and the general public. A customised YouTube channel of the project will be created as soon as the first video is ready for publication.</p>
Partner social media channels	<p>All the project partners are invited to share the project updates and articles via their social media channels and website.</p>

Accountability: ESCI will be responsible for the social media activities through the project channels, such as creating posts, sharing the news and monitoring the outreach. The partners are asked to approach ESCI with relevant news items, ideas, material, etc. and repost the project content through their channels to maximise the impact.

4.3. Project Dissemination Actions

Creating a DC&C strategy with the strongest impact is about making choices. While scientific excellence is a bedrock and exchange and publications are important for ULTIMATE, the project's number one dissemination target audience will be industrial and commercial. They are key to accelerating appraisal and adoption at scale. The challenge is to bring demonstration case innovations from WP1 to life for them – making them credible, visible, and inspirational for individual professionals and organisations. Close collaboration with WP3 living lab engagement in conjunction with local demo site outreach events (i.e. site visits at the large-scale demonstrations) will further fuel this process.

International commercial and environmental impact:

Extending impact and momentum to the target audiences on business & investors and civil society & consumers and beyond requires powerful existing networks. Water Europe and Watershare will lead this for both EU and international audiences. Scheduled B2B meetings between companies, system integrators, solution providers, investors and other participants will take place at Water Market Europe and two additional regional matchmaking events. Internationally, Watershare will further extend the reach of solutions developed in ULTIMATE using their global network of water research organisations and utilities dedicated to applying global expertise to master local water challenges. With members in Japan, South Korea, Indonesia, South Africa, Mexico and more, this forum also regularly exhibits at IWA World Water Congress and other leading events.

4.4. Water Market Europe B2B matchmaking

Water Market Europe is the event cycle that WE has set up to create a unique innovation and business environment, where state of the art water knowledge and research results can meet with market actors and investors within and outside the water sector to create value and new business opportunities. The WME events feature

B2B matchmaking sessions that have succeeded in hosting up to 200 meetings between companies in less than two hours. Each event will bring an average of 75 water and industry companies, professional and investors together for 2 days of discussion and solution matchmaking.

4.5. Collaboration with other Initiatives

Water Europe will connect ULTIMATE to policy makers and framework industrial programs to further help these activities flourish. Their multiple events and advocacy actions engage with decision-makers, thought-leaders and opinion-shapers using ULTIMATE proof points in resource and energy efficiency, industrial symbiosis and digitalisation. Particular attention will be made to connect with the SPIRE 2050 Vision for European process industries and connecting with ULTIMATE demo sites to accelerate ‘hubs for circularity’ - with 15 targeted by 2030 and a total of 50 by 2050 and the EU’ s Water Smart Territories (WST) specialist platform. Task lead KWR and Water Europe, several consortium members are active in leadership initiatives and stakeholder platforms for ULTIMATE results such as ICT4Water, EIP-Water and the Ellen McArthur Foundation members.

Technical outreach to share results and findings with regular exposure in internationally recognised scientific and academic journals will target no less than 10 publications and conference proceedings during the course of the project, an effort coordinated by KWR. The project will fully support EC Open Access Strategy obligations and use of the OpenAIRE and Zenodo platforms to better build research on previously published research results, achieve greater efficiency by fostering collaboration and avoiding duplication and accelerating innovation – particularly towards dynamic SMEs in the consortium and beyond. ESCI will also produce guidelines and coach consortium members to blog, post and advocate achievements with technical presentations and professional social media guidelines.

Communication activities to accelerate transition.

The project will create impact with communication actions to build trust, accelerate transition and make a sustainable change by following these key objectives and principals:

- Create an international network of ambassadors for WSIS from within the project consortium and associated networks – equipping them with clear visuals, substantiated results and in-depth resources.
- Bring ULTIMATE demonstration initiatives, results and events to life through engaging content distributed with a lively editorial calendar, appropriate language and innovative communications channels and tools

- Proactively target audiences where they choose to gather, rather than expecting them to come to us – on and offline—and mix written material with visual and emotional video supports.
- Work with demo sites to localise content and overcome language and cultural barriers.
- Leverage ESCI European network of 500+ science-based journalists and producers and access to science, technology and environment distribution channels.

4.6. Measuring Communication Outreach

ULTIMATE will use a wide range of channels to be visible, credible and ultimately inspire professional and public audiences to take action. ULTIMATE distributes and engages on numerous platforms. Tracking data where possible is important to evaluate actions and impact; but capturing the overall footprint and impact of ULTIMATE across multiple countries is a difficult task. Where media is ‘shared’ and ‘owned’ – such as articles, blogs, twitter, LinkedIn, and website – data and analytics are much easier to track and analyse. However, knowing when a journalist, video news channels or even scientific publisher has cited ULTIMATE (‘earned’ media) is more difficult to achieve.

Figure 8 ULTIMATE segmentation and organisation of communication distribution

ESCI will be responsible for monitoring and assessment of the project communication. The achievement of communication targets will be measured using a variety of sources to achieve the best possible assessment and understanding about how and when

audiences receive and interact with our messages and content. We aim to achieve this via web and social media monitoring.

Below, an example of the data provided by the Falcon tool on the ULTIMATE Twitter performance, as of July 14, 2020, is included.

Figure 9 Example Data on the Performance of Twitter Account

As online communication plays an important role in this project, ESCI will evaluate the impact of the dissemination every six months and review its success and adjust it if needed in M30.

Since online communication tools evolve rapidly, the set of channels and tools in use will be constantly reviewed and updated in case new effective tools for engagement and communication emerge.

All partners will be requested to fill-in a monitoring table, provided by ESCI. It is the responsibility of the partners to keep record of their media communication and update the table regularly. This table will be evaluated every 6 months by ESCI and if needed, used for the adjustment of the DCCMP. A monitoring file in excel has already been established in accordance with the requirements for reporting publications in the participant portal. In M4 a table with responsible persons for monitoring the dissemination activities per partner organisation will be established.

For events, records of numbers of participants will be kept and to get their feedback, of the questionnaires will be used (according to the GDPR).

5. Communication Materials

As the WP6 leader, ESCI will produce communication material to strengthen the impact of the project. This material can be used and adapted to different channels and target groups. This will enable all the project partners to communicate with their national or regional stakeholders in a consistent way.

At project level, a series of materials will be produced to illustrate the reuse of wastewater, and the respective energy and material recovery schemes, with additional publications dedicated to the business models behind them.

Table 6 ULTIMATE Outreach Materials

Material	Description
1 Action post card	Accompanies to attract audiences on the website launch in M3.
1 Postcard Flyer	Build on tangible results and experiences from the case studies in year 3 or 4.
Roll up Poster	For display and visibility at internal and external events.
9 Infographics	A series 9 of infographics will illustrate reuse, energy and material recovery schemes, with additional publications dedicated to the business models on which they are based.
3 Guides for industries	For the reuse of specific technologies.
3 Policy & Market Briefs	Overviews for decision makers and direct them to more detailed resources and contact persons.
1 Commercial Power Point Presentation	Containing overviews of 6 modelling tools and digital solutions from WP2, 3 successful living lab profiles and 3 best practice guidelines from WP3, and 3 circular economy and market briefs from WP4 and WP5.
4 Articles	Articles by independent journalists will display skills, experiences, credibility and performance of the demonstration sites and the project in more detail.
News Bites & Blog Posts	Promoting key project developments and resources to share (2 per month).

12 Quick-fire Interviews	Information on the demonstration and follower site eco-systems and feature people both internal and external to the project consortium.
12 Inspirational Video Profiles	Interviews with key stakeholders and thought leaders inside and out of the consortium to give their assessment and insights on industrial ecology and inspire their peers and fellow industries to doing the same.

In close collaboration with and to amplify Task 3.4, several outreach actions at demo sites will increase the living lab engagement and improve their maturity for industrial impact. They will respect local languages, contexts and cultures with their own info graphics, site visits, webinars, and events. ESCI will oversee and support this process, including local language subtitles for relevant video content.

6. Support of Exploitation through Communication

Successful communication and dissemination are one of the keys to the success for exploitation efforts. Therefore, one key objective is to guarantee professional and public coverage of the project results. Especially at the final phase of the project, with demo sites in place and results available, communication and dissemination activities will focus on the promotion of adoption of the ULTIMATE approaches and technologies. What is more, it will include citizen engagement to foster acceptance and exploitation of the project results.

Moreover, the following work package will be closely collaborating to build a community interested in and committed to further replicate the ULTIMATE solutions in other locations across Europe.

WP4 – Examine the socio-political and governance context for WSIS,

WP5 - Explore new business models and arrangements,

WP6 - Communicate, connect, create synergies and support learning and policy,

WP1 – Demonstrate technologies & systems for water-smart resource-efficient symbiosis.

The Communication and dissemination efforts will aim to improve the attractiveness of Water-Smart Industrial Symbiosis and circular economy. This community will be instrumental for the exploitation of the ULTIMATE results.

Annex 1: Selected WP6 Metrics

	Selected Dissemination, Communication, and Collaboration Actions & Metrics			
DC&C Objectives	M1-12	M13-24	M25-36	M37-48
DC&C Plan	Define strategic plan for success	Monitor and Analyse (M20-24)	Refine and update (M25)	Monitor, refine and update (M40)
Compelling written content for multiplier distribution to specialists & mass media	24 news bits & blog posts 3 interviews 1 independent articles	24 news bits & blog posts 3 interviews 1 independent articles	24 news bits & blog posts 3 interviews 1 independent articles	24 news bits & blog posts 3 interviews 1 independent articles
Innovative video content targeting TV & social media uptake	social media reach	continued social media reach 6 (re)promotion	continued social media reach 6 (re)promotion	1 VNR broadcast continued social media reach 6 (re)promotion
Infographics	9 infographics M12			
ULTIMATE case studies Proprietary and published insights and best practices	Developing format, concepts and opportunities to profile and contribute	3x externally published profiles	3x externally published profiles	3x externally published profiles
ULTIMATE print material Distribution at international, EU & local events, academics	Postcard 1: 500 prints Roll-up poster accompany website launch in M3 1 A1 poster			Postcard 2: 500 prints
Social media strategy Digital distribution targeting consolidated platforms	Twitter: 150 followers / 40 RT LinkedIn: 80 followrs / 20 posts YouTube: 1000 views	Twitter: 300 followers / 30 RT LinkedIn: 160 followrs / 40 posts YouTube: 2000 views	Twitter: 400 followers / 40 RT LinkedIn: 220 followrs / 60 posts YouTube: 2500 views	Twitter: 500 followers / 60 RT LinkedIn: 280 followrs / 80 posts YouTube: 3000 views
Project Website Digital "anchor" for project	Website launch M3 web-statistics: 300 visits / months	web-statistics: 400 visits / month	web-statistics: 400 visits / month	web-statistics: 400 visits / month
Visual identity	uniform deployment infographic creativity	uniform deployment	uniform deployment	uniform deployment
National & International events / year Local stakeholders, citizen, EU, scientific & business	COP meetings EU policy meetings Demonstrator outreach actions Living lab events International collaborations Academic & industry conferences	COP meetings EU policy meetings Demonstrator outreach actions Living lab events International collaborations Academic & industry conferences	COP meetings EU policy meetings Demonstrator outreach actions Living lab events International collaborations Academic & industry conferences	COP meetings EU policy meetings Demonstrator outreach actions Living lab events International collaborations Academic & industry conferences

